

Capital structure and CEO tenure in microfinance institutions*

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Main message

There is a positive association between CEO tenure and the debt proportion of microfinance institutions.

Key points

Microfinance institutions need improved access to debt capital to cover a huge and increasing world demand for microfinance services.

More experienced CEOs may be more aligned with the microfinance institution's mission and they may have a better understanding of the business model of microfinance.

Capital providers may require a proven track record within the institution to supply funding.

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Introduction

While much research efforts have been put into understanding whether poor people benefit from accessing financial services, less is known about the management and finance - and the interaction of the two - of Microfinance institutions (MFIs). This is unfortunate because the management of MFIs will affect capital availability for the microbanking industry, and the capital availability potentially has considerable and direct influence on the industry's customer impact (Tchuigoua et al., 2017). The little MFI-management research available finds evidence of a significant chief executive officer (CEO) influence on MFI performance (Galema et al., 2012; Randøy et al., 2015). This paper aims at making a contribution in this field as it studies the relationship between CEO tenure and the MFI's capital structure.

Although this issue has been studied in other contexts of non-financial firms (e.g., John & Litov, 2010) and traditional banks (e.g., Yeh, 2011), it is of particular relevance to microfinance because increased leverage and tapping into capital markets is considered necessary to cover a huge and increasing world demand for microfinance services (Ledgerwood et al., 2013). Therefore, it is possible to argue that in many ways the most successful MFI CEO is the one that can attract the most debt possible to the organization under his/her management. This study is further a direct response to the call for research issued by, e.g., Tchuigoua (2015) requesting more knowledge on how managers influence MFIs' capital structure.

The setting for this study is different from previous research settings studying the managerial influence on a firm's capital structure. MFIs are organizations that provide small loans and other financial services to economically poor families to support their entrepreneurial activities (Bruhn et al., 2012; Earne & Sherk, 2013). Availability of credit motivates economically poor persons to seek out and identify business opportunities within their economic system (Milana & Ashta, 2012; Bruhn et al., 2012). In this way, access to

financial services is recognized as a tool to fight poverty (Armendariz & Morduch, 2010; Ashta, 2012). MFIs are therefore considered to be ‘social enterprises’ or ‘hybrid organizations’, i.e. firms with both social and financial objectives (Ashta & Hudon, 2012; Battilana & Dorado, 2010).

The demand for microcredit is huge and on average MFIs have reported growth rates of more than 30 percent during most of the years over the last couple of decades, which is around three times that of Western banks (Mersland & Strøm, 2012). Continued high growth is likely as several market opportunities for MFIs remain untapped (Randøy et al., 2015). Furthermore, huge populations still have no access to banking services in their neighborhoods (De Koker, 2013).

Continued microfinance growth depends not only on customer demand but also on MFIs’ access to funding. In the 1970s and 1980s, MFIs operated as social organizations. They provided banking services to the poorest families who traditional commercial banks considered too risky clients (Earne & Sherk, 2013; Milana & Ashta, 2012). The loans were financed primarily with donations provided by generous philanthropist and development agencies (Ghosh & Van Tassel, 2011). Donors were motivated by the possibility of poverty alleviation through the provision of small loans to low-income families (Fehr & Hishigsuren, 2006). Debt financing was not emphasized as access to donor funding prevailed, and most MFIs were operating with non-profit status (Jegers & Verschueren, 2006). However, these forms of organizations soon started to face funding constraints (Fehr & Hishigsuren, 2006). Access to donations and subsidies did not match the huge demand for microcredits by low-income families (Gosh & Van Tassel, 2013; Ashta & Hudon, 2012).

To accommodate new sources of capital, many MFIs underwent changes, for example, by becoming regulated and integrated into the formal financial sector, and to shift their incorporation from non-profit entities to shareholder-owned banks (Fehr & Hishigsuren,

2006; Daher & Le Saout, 2013). Such a shift expanded MFIs sources of capital to include funders from both local and international contexts in the category of individuals, commercial banks, institutional investors, and private equity funds (Earne & Sherk, 2013; Astha, 2012). Most of these new funders demand market returns from the MFIs; hence they can be considered as commercial investors (Earne & Sherk, 2013; Fehr & Hishigsuren, 2006). In total, commercial debt-investments in the microfinance industry increased by seven billion from 2007 to 2010 (Sapundzhieva, 2011).

Overall, MFIs need debt to grow their portfolios to fulfill their missions of expanding their services to more poor clients; “Funding is crucial to improving financial inclusion” (Tchuigoua et al., 2017, p. 133). The question we seek to answer in this paper is whether the tenure of the CEO influences the MFI’s intake of debt. This is an unanswered question not only in the microfinance literature but also in the social enterprise literature in general. While traditional agency theory predicts that CEOs with longer tenure will avoid debt financing because it includes stricter control by debt holders and increases bankruptcy risk (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), several arguments that suggest a *positive* association between debt financing and CEO tenure can be presented for MFIs, or in more general terms, social enterprises. For instance, more experienced CEOs may be more aligned with the MFI’s mission and they may have a better understanding of the business model of microfinance. Moreover, given the entrepreneurial characteristics of the microfinance industry, capital providers may require a proven track record within the bank to supply funding. As discussed in the paper, all these aspects may lead to higher debt levels among experienced CEOs, contrary to the predictions drawn based on traditional agency theory.

The empirical findings of this paper support the view that financing choices of MFIs are influenced by the profile of the managers. Specifically, the results show that the CEO tenure has a positive and significant effect on the MFI’s debt ratio. In a young industry like

microfinance, we do not consider this finding surprising though important for policy makers and boards of MFIs. In more general terms, our results contribute to a growing strand of literature suggesting that standard management and governance theories on how to control CEOs may not be valid when applied on hybrid organizations operating with both a financial logic and a social logic (Battilana & Lee, 2014).

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Following this introduction, the next section presents a literature review and hypotheses. We then outline the research design. We continue with a discussion of descriptive statistics. Thereafter, we present the empirical results and analyses. The final section discusses the results and concludes the paper.

Literature review and hypotheses

Though Modigliani and Miller (1958) put forward the theory of capital structure and its irrelevance for the value of the firm, subsequent literature often struggles to confirm the theory. If the capital structure is not irrelevant, the determinants of capital structure become an important research question. However, prior studies do not provide conclusive evidence as to which are the determinants of a firm's capital structure (Tchuiigoua et al., 2017). Barton and Gordon (1987) posit that managerial choices, in general, can help to explain the level of debt in the capital structure. Recent theories argue that managers avoid contracting debt to protect their jobs, to shield away from debt covenants, and ease the raising of equity capital (Douglas, 2002).

Agency theory predicts conflict of objectives between the agent, i.e., the CEO, and the principals, i.e., owners, debt providers, and donors (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Likewise, there can be a conflict between different types of principals. For example, equity holders may prefer financing more projects with debt as long as the project will result in higher returns (Myers & Majluf, 1984) while funders with development objectives (e.g., donors) may see

this as risky (Conning, 1999). Therefore, several types of stakeholders may influence a firm's financial behavior.

However, and what is the core of this paper, is that a firm's financing choices and capital structure are likely to be significantly influenced by the motivations and profile of a firm's CEO (Barton & Gordon, 1987; Hackbarth, 2008). Financing with debt requires sufficient cash flow to allow for the payments of instalments and interests. In the case of losses, there is no profit distribution to equity holders while debt holders must be paid. As such, financing with debt is associated with a higher possibility of bankruptcy of the firm which obviously is risky to the job of the CEO (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Agency theory predicts that CEOs become increasingly entrenched as they gain experience in their positions and according to this theory, we should expect a negative relationship between the MFI's debt ratio and the tenure of its CEO (John & Litov, 2010)

The risk involved in debt financing is the most reasonable explanation for the findings in many empirical studies that there is a negative relationship between the tenure of the CEO and the firm's intake of debt (Berger et al., 1997; Chen et al., 2010). A long tenure exposes the CEO to various stimuli relevant to decision-making that ensure their survival in the position (Hambrick & Fukutomi, 1991) and as time passes, the CEOs become wary of any financial risk that may jeopardize their jobs (Chen et al., 2010; Hambrick & Fukutomi, 1991).

However, another stream of capital structure theories suggests that managers maintain high debt ratios to discourage takeovers, to justify their ability to generate sufficient income to cover operating expenses and to repay other debts (Israel, 1992). High debt ratios can also be related to the pecking order theory; the pecking order theory says that companies prioritize their sources of funding according to the cost of the funding (Myers, 1984). Internal financing is, according to the pecking order theory, the preferred source of financing, but when external

financing is needed, debt is preferred to equity. Due to its high cost, (externally raised) equity is a financing means of last resort.

It is likely that CEOs of MFIs follow a pecking order because retained profits, subsidies and donations do not match the huge demand of microcredits by low-income families (Gosh & Van Tassel, 2013; Tchuigoua, 2015). Experienced CEOs may to an even larger extent follow a pecking order because longevity of tenure in the position increases CEOs' discretionary power in general (Berger et al., 1997), as well as their influence on firms' financing (Hambrick & Fukutomi, 1991). Moreover, other characteristics of the microfinance industry may provide additional arguments for a positive relationship between CEO tenure and debt financing.

First of all, microfinance is considered a development enhancing industry providing financial services that may improve poor customers' quality of life. MFIs are thus hybrid organizations with both financial and social objectives. Such an industry may be attractive for managers with broader and more social oriented motivations compared to managers of commercial firms (Battilana & Dorado, 2010). Besley and Ghatak (2005) theorize on how mission-oriented organizations, like MFIs, are staffed and managed by 'motivated agents' who work for the fulfillment of the organizations' missions. Randøy et al. (2015) test this theory on microfinance data and find that in particular founders of MFIs can be considered motivated agents in the sense put forward by Besley and Ghatak (2005). In line with the finding in Randøy et al. (2015) it can be argued that the more tenured a CEO is, the more aligned he/she will be with the MFI's mission of reaching out to as many customers as possible (Conning, 1999).

Considering increased discretionary power following longer tenure it can well be argued that MFIs managed by CEOs with longer tenure will have higher ratios of debts compared to MFIs managed by less tenured CEOs. Taken together, we argue that CEOs in

hybrid organizations become more aligned over time with the missions of the organizations they manage, and in MFIs such alignment may result in a willingness to take on more debt in order to reach out to more clients with microloans.

Another argument for a positive relationship between CEO tenure and use of debt financing is the fact that the microfinance industry is a new industry and MFIs can be considered entrepreneurial firms (Randøy et al., 2015). In such situations, investors may be more reluctant to provide funds when the CEO has relatively short tenure. It is well known that investors when considering investing in entrepreneurial firms evaluate the CEO and the management team more thoroughly compared to when investors consider well-established enterprises where previous years' results and traditional financial indicators play a significant role in investment decisions (Ghosh & Van Tassel, 2011). Investors need time to get to know the CEO, which may lead to less debt leverage in MFIs managed by CEOs with shorter tenure in their positions.

A third argument for increased debt levels in MFIs with more experienced CEOs is the fact that the microfinance business model is complicated and it takes time for a new hired CEO, especially if he/she has no previous microfinance experience, to learn it. Client screening and monitoring is different from traditional banking since it depends mainly on the judgments of the credit officer and little on formal documentation (Armendariz & Morduch, 2010). In such a situation an inexperienced CEO will probably be reluctant to increase the intake of debt until understanding better the MFI's business model. Moreover, liability management is still not core in most MFIs (Lapie & Mersland, 2011). Most of the managers' attention is still devoted to asset management, i.e. loan portfolio management and the risk within. It is, therefore, reasonable to believe that CEOs with less experience in their jobs will have less time available to seek out more debt opportunities.

Taken together, traditional governance literature on the relationship between CEO tenure and debt leverage predicts a negative relationship between the CEO's tenure and the MFI's debt ratio. However, since MFIs are hybrid organizations it can be argued that their CEOs over time improve their knowledge on the microfinance business model and become increasingly aligned with the organization's mission; these factors could lead to a positive relationship between the MFI's debt ratio and the CEO's tenure. Moreover, since MFIs are entrepreneurial firms, investors might be more willing to provide loans to organizations with more experienced CEOs. Because traditional agency theory and more specific theories on microfinance and hybrid organizations to some extent contradict, we present hypotheses for both a positive and a negative relationship between the CEO's tenure and the MFI's debt ratio (stated as alternative hypotheses to the null hypothesis of no association):

Hypothesis 1a: There is a positive relationship between an MFI's debt ratio and the tenure of its CEO.

Hypothesis 1b: There is a negative relationship between an MFI's debt ratio and the tenure of its CEO.

Given the ambiguity of the theory, all tests will be two-sided.

Research design

The sample

This study uses secondary data from the five largest rating agencies specialized in the assessment of MFIs. The five rating agencies include MicroRate, Microfinanza, Planet Rating, Crisil and M-Cril. There are no differences in the rating agencies' methods relevant for the variables included in this study (for more details on the microfinance ratings, see Beisland and Mersland, 2012). The rating reports are publicly available at the rating agencies' websites or at www.ratingfund2.org.

In our sample, a large firm bias is avoided because the very largest MFIs operating as commercial banks are excluded from the dataset as traditional rating agencies like Standards and Poor and similar agencies rate these. Moreover, the dataset does not include small savings and credit cooperatives or development programs offering credit to poor people as part of their social services. Overall, the MFIs included are typical representatives of professional providers of microfinance services.

We follow a procedure by Hambrick and Quigley (2014) of excluding CEOs with one year or less in the firm; the CEO needs some tenure before it is reasonable to expect a CEO effect. We further exclude observations of MFIs managed by CEOs with more than or equal to 20 years of experience since in such an MFI, CEO effects normally are difficult to separate from firm effects (Hambrick & Quigley, 2014). The final sample makes up a panel dataset containing information for up to six consecutive years from 453 MFIs located in 76 countries collected from 1996 to 2011.

Measurement and definition of variables

Dependent variable: Capital Structure

Similar to prior studies, we use the ratio of total debts to total assets as our measure of capital structure (e.g., Berger et al., 1997) and the core dependent variable applied in this study. Market values are not available for the unlisted MFIs of our sample, hence the values of total debts and total assets are based on book values that are reported in the rating reports. Because some MFIs engage in deposit taking, the amount of total debt includes the deposit amount accepted as voluntary savings.

Test variable: The CEO's tenure

The CEO's tenure is a personal trait defined as the longevity in a position (Chen et al., 2010; Hambrick & Fukutomi, 1991). The focus is on the CEO because of his/her highest

position among the top management team (Hambrick & Fukutomi, 1991). The numbers of years of the CEO in position represent the measure of tenure (Berger et al., 1997).

Control variables

The selected control variables account for variations in capital structure that are not to be attributed to variations in CEO tenure. Because the study pertains to observations that have been collected from several countries, we include country-level control variables in addition to firm-level variables. The firm control variables include variables at the CEO level as well as at the MFI level.

CEO control variables include CEO founder status, CEO duality status, and CEO gender status. When the CEO is also the founder of the firm, he or she is often the psychological owner of the firm. This psychological ownership creates a structural power that induces personal feelings of responsibility and strong attachment to the firm's decision-making (Van Dyne & Pierce, 2004). In this context, a founder CEO may to a larger extent than a hired CEO influence financing choices (Galema et al., 2012). Finkelstein (1992) argues that holding the two title positions of CEO and chair of the board by the same person defines the CEO's structural power in an organization and we expect that CEO-duality is a characteristic that potentially can influence MFIs' financing as well. Additionally, the gender of the CEO might influence the level of external financing of a firm; in the microfinance literature studies have looked into whether having a female CEO influences the MFI performance and they find a positive association in this relationship (e.g., Strøm, et al., 2014).

When it comes to MFI control variables, we first include 'tangible assets' measured as the ratio of net fixed assets to total assets (Tchuigoua, 2015). Debt capacity may be influenced by the amount of fixed assets available to serve as a guarantee for debt (Barclay et al., 2006). Likewise, we control for the MFI's loan focus measured as the gross loan portfolio to total assets ratio (Tchuigoua, 2015). We further include MFI profitability measured as return on

assets (ROA) (Mersland & Strøm, 2009). To control for the MFI's risk, we include portfolio at risk for 30 days (PaR30) (Daher & Le Saout, 2013). It can be expected that MFIs with a larger share of their portfolios at risk are unattractive to external funders and thus will have less leverage in their capital structure, see evidence from the banking literature (Gropp & Heider, 2010). Empirical evidence in MFIs indicates a significant positive relationship between size (total assets) and external financing (Tchuigoua, 2015). Size is controlled for in this study as well, and similarly to other studies we use total assets to proxy for size.

In the microfinance industry, several types of ownership coexist (Mersland, 2009) – a characteristic that needs to be controlled for in the empirical investigation. While MFIs owned by shareholders are allowed to distribute profits to their shareholders, MFIs organized as Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) or member-based cooperatives do not have shareholders and typically do not distribute profits (Mersland, 2009). Moreover, shareholder-owned MFIs may more easily access additional equity compared to NGOs that need to turn to donors or cooperatives dependent on members that are also their customers. Therefore, ownership type may have an effect on the MFI capital structure.

The age of an MFI indicates its accumulated business experience. Older MFIs are probably likely to have better access to capital compared to younger ones. This study uses the number of years since microfinance startup as a control for the MFI's experience. We further include a dummy variable indicating whether the MFI is allowed to mobilize savings from local depositors. Such a possibility gives the MFI an additional source of debt to finance its credit operations and should, therefore, be controlled for. Moreover, board size is included as a control variable because larger boards have larger networks and may influence an MFI's access to external finance (Stearns & Mizruchi, 1993).

To control for country effects we first include a self-constructed proxy for the microfinance market competition in the country in which the MFI is situated. Similar to

Mersland et al. (2011) we also include the Heritage Index of Economic Freedom which is a composite measure of a country's Rule of Law, Government's economic involvement, Regulatory efficiency and level of Market Openness; all important elements considered by investors before making an investment. Table 1 shows definitions and measurements of all variables used in the study. Because of right skewness, we apply a logarithmic transformation to the tangible assets, loan focus and the total assets variables.

Table 1

Methods

Empirical studies on CEO characteristics and their effects on capital structure face a familiar challenge of omitted variable bias and endogeneity. The omitted variable bias can manifest on the CEO level. For instance, other CEO characteristics (e.g., CEO founder status, CEO duality, CEO gender) that correlate with the CEO tenure may influence our results, thus, as mentioned, we control for these variables. Endogeneity may be a problem due to the presence of firms' unobserved heterogeneity. Such heterogeneity may simultaneously explain the firm's characteristics - the CEO tenure as well as the firm's capital structure decision. To account for such problems, we estimate the following general dynamic panel model (Baltagi, 2008);

$$y_{it} = \gamma y_{i,t-1} + \beta' x_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

$$\varepsilon_{it} = \eta_i + v_{it}$$

Where y_{it} is the dependent variable, $y_{i,t-1}$ is the lagged dependent variable, γ is the coefficient on the lagged dependent variable, β is the column vector of coefficients, x_{it} is the $k \times 1$ vector of independent variables, the error term has two components; η_i is the time constant fixed effects (unobserved), and v_{it} is the idiosyncratic error.

The dynamic panel data regression is estimated using the generalized method of moments (GMM). To implement the GMM, we follow a procedure outlined by Roodman

(2009). In our panel data, the debt ratio represents the dependent variable measured repeatedly within an MFI on an annual basis. Hence, we cluster the models at the MFI level. Likewise, GMM assumes no autocorrelation in the residuals, hence, we include time dummies (years) in the models (Roodman, 2009).

Descriptive statistics

In Table 2 we report descriptive statistics for dependent and independent variables. On average 39 percent of the total assets are financed with debts. The average CEO tenure in our sample is slightly less than seven years. 34 percent of the CEOs are founders, 26 percent are female and 14 percent are also the chair of the board. The average MFI has seven board members.

Table 2

Moreover, in Table 2 the average return on assets is 2 percent, and portfolio at risk (PaR30) is 5 percent. Of the MFI's total assets, 5 percent are comprised of tangible (fixed) assets. The loan focus ratio of 0.78 indicates that gross loans are equal to 78 percent of the total assets. 30 percent of MFIs accept deposits indicating the importance of controlling for this variable in our models. 38 percent of the MFIs are organized as shareholder firms and these include banks or non-bank financial institutions. The remaining are either member based cooperatives or Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). The average of total assets is US\$1.27 million. The average MFI is 12 years old while the oldest started with small agricultural loans already 51 years ago illustrating that the business of microfinance is not a new phenomenon. The mean level of market competition, as assessed based on information in the rating reports, is 4.58 on a 7-point scale.

Results and analysis

In Table 3, we present our results from the dynamic panel-data estimation on the CEO tenure and its effect on the MFI's debt ratio. Results are referred to as significant when the p-value of the regression coefficients is below 0.1. We include explanatory variables successively to test the stability of our results. In Model 1, we run the regression with the CEO tenure only, and the result indicates that CEO tenure has a positive and significant effect on the debt ratio. We add board size and other MFI-specific control variables in Model 2, and the results hold as in Model 1, that is, the CEO tenure has a positive and significant effect on the debt ratio. In Model 3, we add the CEO control variables (CEO=female, CEO=chairperson, and CEO=founder), and the results are similar to those reported in Model 1 and Model 2.

Table 3

In Model 4, we add the country control variables (competition and heritage), and we observe that the coefficient of the CEO tenure remains positive and has a significant effect on the debt ratio. Taken together, the 4 regression specifications suggest consistent and robust results. We note that risk (PaR30) is significantly negatively related to the debt ratio, which is a result we find expected and reasonable. The significantly negative relation between ROA and the debt ratio suggests that more profitable MFIs have less debt – a result somewhat inconsistent with a study of Tchuigoua (2015), which suggests that more profitable MFIs are better able to mobilize local deposits compared to less profitable MFIs. Interestingly, few of the control variables turn out to have a significant relationship with the MFI's debt level; CEO tenure is one of very few explanatory variables that consistently show up as significantly related to the debt ratio in our analysis. This further indicates that the tenure of the CEO is really an important factor when it comes to the MFI's ability to take on debt.

As noted in the previous discussion, in some MFIs, voluntary savings form an important part of the debt. To check the robustness of our results and since most MFIs do not

accept deposits, we re-run all regressions excluding voluntary saving in the debt ratio (not reported). The results mirror those presented in Table 3. The main difference is that the alternative analysis shows an insignificant relationship between the ROA and the debt ratio.

A particularly interesting finding in the robustness test is a significant relationship between the dummy ‘voluntary saving’ and the MFIs’ debt level. Voluntary savings are excluded in this analysis, so the result suggests that MFIs mobilizing voluntary savings are also those best able to attract funding from debt investors. Our explanation of this finding is that MFIs engaged in mobilizing deposits are the most sophisticated and advanced MFIs, hence the MFIs with the best capability to liaison with more professional debt markets. The finding may also be related to what Beisland et al. (2015) refer to as the monitoring effect of savings: the depositors want to keep the MFI viable and therefore monitor the actions of the entity. Such depositor monitoring may be a type of governance mechanism considered favorable by professional debt providers.

Discussions and Conclusion

MFIs face huge demand for their services, in particular loans. To service the high demand for microloans we contend that MFIs need to shift their funding focus from donors to the capital markets (Gosh & Van Tassel, 2013; Tchuigoua et al., 2017). It is therefore relevant to search for factors influencing the MFIs’ ability to attract debt. In this study, we argue that the debt ratio in MFIs is likely to be affected by the profile and motivation of the CEO (Barton & Gordon, 1987). The traditional literature on the relationship between CEO tenure and a firm’s debt level generally predicts that CEOs are being entrenched with time and could shy away from debt. In this paper we also present a rival hypothesis. We argue that MFIs can be considered complex development agencies and that their CEOs with time will increasingly be aligned with the mission to serve as many clients as possible (Besley & Ghatak, 2005).

Moreover, since MFIs are entrepreneurial organizations (Randøy et al., 2015), providers of debt are probably more willing to lend to MFIs with more experienced CEOs.

The result supports the hypothesis that with an increasing tenure, CEOs in MFIs take on more debt. With increased debt levels the MFIs are able to grow and expand their microfinance services. We argue that this finding has important practical implications. Most MFIs are still young and liability management is still not core in their modus operandi (Labie & Mersland, 2011). Faced with high demand for their services MFIs will need to increasingly leverage their equity with debt. This study indicates that increasing leverage levels requires experienced CEOs. Even though MFIs, like those studied in this paper, are normally rated by third party agencies, they still fit the characteristic of entrepreneurial organizations and our results are consistent with the notion that investors depend on a personal trust relationship before deciding to lend to an MFI. Such relationships take time to build resulting in increased leverage for the more experienced CEO.

Also our study could have theoretical implications. The results indicate that the entrenchment theory, i.e., as CEOs gain experience they become increasingly able to obtain personal benefits - for instance in the form of job security - does not necessarily seem to apply for hybrid organizations like MFIs. Rather the opposite seems to be true. When the CEO stays with the organization over time he/she might become aligned with and able to better fulfill its mission. Experienced CEOs seem to search out more opportunities for the MFI, increase its leverage and thereby make further expansion of services possible. Hence, standard management and governance theories on how to control CEOs may not be valid when applied on hybrid organizations.

Of note, our results do not discriminate between different explanations for the findings. Therefore, we cannot say whether the increased debt ratios associated with more experienced CEOs should be attributed to more competent, motivated and mission aligned

CEOs, or to lenders being more willing to provide loans to MFIs managed by more experienced CEOs. There is thus a need for more research on hybrid organizations and whether their CEOs become entrenched or aligned with the missions of their organizations as they gain more experience in their positions. In general there is a need for more research on hybrid organizations and their management and governance systems.

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Table 1: Definition and measurement of variables used in the study

Variable	Definition/measurement
<i>Dependent variable</i>	
Debt ratio	Total debt (book value of debt + Voluntary savings)/Total assets (book value)
<i>Independent test variable</i>	
CEO tenure	Number of years in the CEO position
<i>CEO control variables</i>	
CEO founder	Dummy variable, one if the CEO has founder status, and zero otherwise
CEO chair	Dummy variable, one if the CEO is also chair of the board, and zero otherwise
CEO female	Dummy variable, one if the CEO is female and zero otherwise
<i>MFI specific control variables</i>	
Return on assets	Net income before donations/Average assets
PaR30	Outstanding loan past due for >30 days/Gross outstanding portfolio
Tangible assets	Natural logarithm of (Net fixed assets/Total assets)
Loan focus	Natural logarithm of (Gross loans/Total assets)
Voluntary savings	Dummy variable, 1 if an MFI accepts voluntary deposits, and zero otherwise
Total assets	Natural logarithm of (Total assets)
MFI age	Difference between the observation year and the year of establishment of microfinance activities
Shareholding firm	Dummy variable, one if the MFI is a shareholding firm, and zero otherwise
Board size	Number of board members
<i>Country control variables</i>	
Markets competition	7 point scale where 1 indicates low level and 7 indicates high level of competition in the market where the MFI operates. The variable is constructed based on information in the rating reports.
Heritage	An index that measures the country's degree of economic freedom.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Debt ratio	978	0.39	0.18	0.00	0.64
CEO tenure	805	6.69	4.12	2.00	19.00
Board size	1012	6.75	3.08	1.00	21.00
Return on assets	1041	0.02	0.12	-0.99	0.56
Portfolio at risk for >30 days	959	0.05	0.08	0.00	0.82
Tangible assets	1071	0.05	0.04	0.00	0.38
ln(Tangible assets)	1071	0.04	0.03	0.00	0.29
Loan focus	1075	0.78	0.11	0.07	0.97
ln(loan focus)	1075	0.57	0.07	0.04	0.68
Voluntary saving	1078	0.30	0.46	0.00	1.00
Shareholders firm	1072	0.38	0.48	0.00	1.00
Total assets	1075	1.27	2.57	0.04	20.79
ln(Total assets)	1075	15.32	1.47	10.49	19.45
MFI age	1067	12.40	8.40	1.00	51.00
CEO=female	1078	0.26	0.44	0.00	1.00
CEO=chairperson	1066	0.14	0.35	0.00	1.00
CEO=founder	1080	0.34	0.48	0.00	1.00
Competition	1047	4.58	1.49	1.00	7.00
Heritage	862	56.41	6.80	0.532	0.78

Note: In Table 2, total assets are in US dollar millions.

Table 3: Dynamic panel-data estimation, one-step system GMM: CEO tenure and its effect on the Debt ratio

Dependent variable	Debt ratio=[Total debt+voluntary savings/Total assets]							
	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4	
CEO=tenure	0.006**	(2.051)	0.010**	(2.378)	0.015**	(2.172)	0.013**	(2.032)
Board size			0.004	(1.598)	0.005	(1.627)	0.001	(0.222)
Return on assets			-0.151	(-)	-0.147	(-)	-0.167*	(-)
				1.614)		1.567)		1.795)
Portfolio at risk for >30 days			-0.212	(-)	-0.303**	(-)	-0.351**	(-)
				1.398)		2.042)		2.333)
ln(tangible assets)			0.017	(0.996)	0.016	(0.909)	0.022	(1.377)
ln(loan focus)			0.035	(0.509)	0.037	(0.546)	0.034	(0.488)
Voluntary saving			0.138**	(2.366)	0.136**	(2.463)	0.128**	(2.241)
Shareholders firm			0.086	(1.052)	0.094	(1.026)	0.082	(0.973)
ln(total assets)			0.027	(0.554)	0.041	(0.713)	0.010	(0.219)
MFI age			0.002	(0.372)	0.001	(0.088)	0.001	(0.157)
CEO=Female					-0.003	(-)	0.006	(0.225)
						0.114)		
CEO=Chairperson					-0.150	(-)	-0.186	(-)
						1.278)		1.215)
CEO=Founder					-0.089	(-)	-0.067	(-)
						1.537)		1.269)
Competition							-0.012**	(-)
								2.034)
Heritage							-0.045	(-)
								0.528)
(Debt ratio) _{i,t-1}	0.588***	(7.189)	0.637***	(7.015)	0.621***	(6.429)	0.595***	(6.546)
Constant	0.128	(1.630)	0.496	(0.798)	0.762	(1.022)	0.348	(0.602)
Time dummies	Yes		Yes		Yes		Yes	
Observations	695		693		687		687	
Number of MFIs	221		220		217		217	
F-statistic p-value	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000	
Hansen p-value	0.239		0.155		0.137		0.123	
Sargan p-value	0.163		0.160		0.144		0.157	
Arellano-Bond test for AR(1)	0.000		0.001		0.001		0.001	
Arellano-Bond test for AR(2)	0.320		0.519		0.511		0.645	

Note: In Table 3, we report coefficients, and robust t-statistics in parentheses. ***, **, and * denote 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1 significance levels.

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